

ANALYSIS OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY IN ELECTRICITY GENERATION AT NATURAL GAS PRESSURE REDUCTION STATIONS

¹Arsen Mukolyants, ²Irina Sotnikova, ³Dilbar Ergasheva

¹Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) of Technical Sciences, Associate Professor of the Department of "Hydropower and hydraulics" Tashkent State Technical University

²Associate Professor of the Department of Nuclear Power Plants and Thermal Power Engineering Tashkent State Technical University

³Candidate of Technical Sciences, Associate Professor of the Department of Machines and Equipment for the Oil and Gas Industry and Pipeline Transport, Tashkent State Technical University

¹ORCID 0000-0001-8774-7243, ²ORCID 0009-0007-8667-8857, ³ORCID 0000-0001-6243-6529

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One of the simplest methods of heating gas before the expander is the use of a specialized boiler (Fig. 1).

Fig.1. EGU with gas heating in the boiler: 1 - manometer measuring the inlet pressure of the unit, 2 - reducing device, 3 - manometer measuring the outlet pressure from the unit, 4 - boiler for gas heating, 5 - flue for exhaust gas discharge, 6 - manometer measuring the pressure before the expander-generator, 7 - expander, 8 - generator, 9 - manometer measuring the pressure after the expander-generator.

The results of calculating the specific fuel consumption for electricity generation, performed using formula (1), are shown in the graph (Fig. 2). The results demonstrate the dependence of the specific flow rate on the temperature of the gas in front of the expander and the different inlet pressures of the gas into the expander at fixed values. ($p_2 = 1,5 \text{ kg/cm}^2$ and $\eta_b = 0,9$).

Fig.2. Specific fuel consumption for electricity generation.

The graph indicates that the gas temperature has a minimal impact on specific fuel consumption. The efficiency of the boiler used for heating the gas significantly influences the change in fuel consumption.

If the change in the enthalpy of the gas at the inlet to the gas-consuming unit does not affect the gas consumption, the formulas are simplified and take the following form:

Table 1. The results of calculating the power of a gas turbine installation, increasing fuel consumption and boiler gas consumption at initial and final gas temperatures

$t_1, ^\circ\text{C}$	T_1, K	T_2, K	$N_{\text{UNIT}}, \text{kW}$	$G_{\text{fuel}}, \text{kg/s}$	$\Delta G, \text{kg/s}$
5	278,15	218,03	321,789	2,564	0,0065
10	283,15	221,95	340,913	2,565	0,0070
20	293,15	229,78	379,589	2,566	0,0081
30	303,15	237,62	418,851	2,567	0,0092
40	313,15	245,46	458,634	2,568	0,0104
50	323,15	253,30	499,084	2,569	0,1150
60	333,15	261,14	540,211	2,570	0,0127
70	343,15	268,98	582,061	2,571	0,0138
80	353,15	276,81	624,695	2,573	0,0150
90	363,15	284,65	668,030	2,574	0,0162
100	373,15	292,49	712,118	2,575	0,0175
110	383,15	300,33	757,003	2,576	0,0187
120	393,15	308,17	802,695	2,578	0,0200
130	403,15	316,01	849,193	2,579	0,0213
140	413,15	323,85	896,516	2,580	0,0226
150	423,15	331,68	944,654	2,581	0,0239

Thus, the calculation results of relative power for different gas preheating options showed that the highest power is achieved when using exhaust gases from the gas turbine unit as a heat source. Calculations of specific fuel consumption for electricity generation at different pressures and heating temperatures indicated that, at low gas preheating temperatures, using a boiler for heating is a more economical option. However, as the gas heating temperature increases, using exhaust gases from the gas turbine unit becomes more economically justified, as it significantly reduces fuel costs and improves the overall system efficiency.